

Chemical speciation of Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of L-glutamic acid in 1,4-dioxan-water mixtures

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Manuscript received 15 September 2011, revised 08 November 2011, accepted 21 November 2011

Abstract : Chemical speciation of Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of L-glutamic acid in 0.0–60.0% v/v 1,4-dioxan-water mixtures at an ionic strength of 0.16 mol L^{-1} and 303 K has been studied pH metrically. The active forms of the ligand are LH_3^+ , LH_2 , LH^- and L^{2-} . The predominant species detected are $\text{ML}_2\text{H}_4^{2+}$, ML_2H_3^+ , ML_2H_2 , ML_2H^- and ML_2^{2-} . The trend in variation of complex stability constants with change in the dielectric constant of the medium is explained on the basis of electrostatic and non-electrostatic forces.

Keywords : Complex equilibria, chemical speciation, L-glutamic acid, 1,4-dioxan, metals.

Introduction

L-Glutamic acid (Glu) is a non-essential amino acid and present in many foods either in free form or in peptides and proteins¹. It acts as a neurotransmitter for the central nervous system, brain and spinal cord. It is used in the treatment of epilepsy, mental retardation, muscular dystrophy and ulcers^{2,3}. Hence, speciation studies of Glu with Ca, Mg and Zn in DOX-water mixtures are reported in the present communication. 1,4-Dioxan (DOX) is an aprotic solvent capable of acting as hydrogen bond acceptor with random structure⁴. The protonation constants of Glu in DOX-water mixtures have been reported earlier⁵.

Results and discussion

Stability constants of M^{II} -Glu complexes in DOX-water mixture are given in Table 1. Very low standard deviation in overall stability constants ($\log \beta$) signifies the precision of these constants.

Effect of solvent :

The linear trends of stability constant ($\log \beta$) values of complexes of Glu with $1/D$ (D is the dielectric constant of the medium) of DOX-water mixture indicate that the dielectric constant is responsible for the stability trend and electrostatic forces are dominant over non-electrostatic forces⁶.

Table 1. Parameters of best fit chemical models of Glu complexes with Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} and Zn^{II} in DOX-water mixtures

% v/v DOX	$\log \beta_{\text{mlh}}$ (SD)				
	120	121	122	123	124
	Ca^{II}				
0.0	4.71(12)	15.68(10)	25.77(6)	30.49(12)	34.64(10)
10.0	3.39(73)	14.22(25)	23.64(20)	28.93(14)	33.14(6)
20.0	3.73(29)	14.33(18)	23.58(27)	30.14(5)	34.35(4)
30.0	5.36(14)	15.88(14)	25.17(14)	30.21(16)	34.33(16)
40.0	6.59(10)	16.23(14)	25.72(10)	30.53(16)	34.77(22)
50.0	5.25(11)	15.58(13)	24.97(15)	30.36(19)	34.90(25)
60.0	5.09(11)	16.05(11)	25.33(16)	31.13(18)	35.83(28)
	Mg^{II}				
0.0	3.58(36)	14.57(13)	24.39(7)	29.07(7)	32.79(8)
10.0	4.31(12)	14.34(14)	23.61(16)	28.40(15)	32.19(23)
20.0	5.96(9)	15.84(11)	25.07(10)	29.79(11)	33.68(12)
30.0	4.89(7)	14.98(10)	24.37(11)	29.65(10)	33.43(22)
40.0	6.28(4)	16.21(5)	25.48(5)	30.29(9)	34.64(8)
50.0	6.19(6)	16.44(7)	25.48(6)	30.46(12)	35.18(10)
60.0	5.31(6)	15.81(8)	25.14(12)	30.93(14)	35.53(27)
	Zn^{II}				
0.0	9.32(13)	17.37(17)	23.74(42)	28.51(30)	32.39(36)
10.0	9.35(18)	17.37(23)	24.07(43)	29.06(34)	33.25(33)
20.0	9.82(14)	17.75(18)	24.23(34)	29.38(26)	33.45(37)
30.0	9.91(9)	17.96(10)	24.62(13)	29.61(18)	33.67(25)
40.0	12.11(6)	19.77(5)	26.14(4)	30.61(10)	35.13(6)
50.0	11.08(10)	18.85(10)	25.45(10)	30.01(39)	34.85(25)
60.0	10.51(4)	18.44(5)	25.26(8)	30.88(12)	35.64(18)

Distribution diagrams :

Glu has two dissociable protons and one amino group which can associate with a proton. It exists as LH_3^+ at low pH and gets deprotonated with the formation of LH_2 , LH^- and L^{2-} successively with increase in pH, in the pH ranges 2.0–6.0, 3.0–11.0 and above 8.0, respectively. Hence, the binary metal-ligand complexes predicted and refined are ML_2 , ML_2H , ML_2H_2 , ML_2H_3 and ML_2H_4 for Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} and Zn^{II} . The formation of various complexes is shown in the following equilibria.

Some typical distribution diagrams of binary complexes of Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} and Zn^{II} with Glu in DOX-water mixtures are shown in Fig. 1. The species ML_2^{2-} , ML_2H^- , ML_2H_2 , ML_2H_3^+ and $\text{ML}_2\text{H}_4^{2+}$ are formed in the pH range 2.5–11.0. The ML_2H_4 is formed from free metal and LH_3^+

form of the ligand (Equilibrium 1) below a pH of 5.0. The species ML_2H_3 is formed either from free metal and LH_3^+ (Equilibrium 2) or by the deprotonation of ML_2H_4 (Equilibrium 3) below a pH of 6.0. Similarly ML_2H_2 can be formed through Equilibria 4 and 5 beyond 4.0 pH. From Fig. 1, the formation of ML_2H_2 from M^{II} and LH_3^+ is ruled out since the concentration of LH_3^+ is negligible in the pH range of formation of ML_2H_2 . The species ML_2H and ML_2 are formed either through successive deprotonation of ML_2H_2 (Equilibria 6 and 8) or from free metal and the ligand (Equilibria 7 and 9) above a pH of 5.0.

Materials and methods :

0.05 mol L^{-1} solutions of L-glutamic acid, Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} and Zn^{II} chlorides (Merck, Germany) were prepared in triple-distilled deionised water by maintaining 0.05 mol L^{-1} hydrochloric acid to increase the solubility and to suppress the hydrolysis of metal salts. DOX (Qualigens, India) was used as received. 0.2 mol L^{-1} Hydrochloric acid (Qualigens, India) was prepared. 2.0 mol L^{-1} Sodium chloride (Merck, India) was prepared to maintain the ionic strength in the titrand. 0.4 mol L^{-1} Sodium hydroxide (Merck, India) was prepared. All the solutions were standardized by standard methods. To assess the errors that might have crept into the determination of the concentrations, the data were subjected to analysis of variance of one way classification⁷. The strengths of alkali and mineral acid were determined using the Gran plot method⁸.

The titrimetric data were obtained by using calibrated ELICO (Model LI-120) pH meter (readability 0.01) at 303.0 ± 0.1 K and 0.16 mol L^{-1} ionic strength. The equilibration of glass electrode in DOX-water mixtures (0.0–60.0% v/v), calibration of the instrument and other experimental details are given elsewhere⁶. The computer programs SCPHD⁹ and MINQUAD75¹⁰ were used to calculate the correction factor and the binary stability constants, respectively.

Acknowledgement

The authors (BAK, SR, KBK) thank the University Grants Commission, New Delhi, India for financial support under Faculty Development Programme.

Fig. 1. Distribution diagrams of binary complexes of Glu in 40% v/v DOX-water mixture. (A) Ca^{II} , (B) Mg^{II} and (C) Zn^{II} .

Note

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